

ACUTE - Accessibility and Connectivity Knowledge Hub for Urban Transformation in Europe

WP2 – Research synthesis

D2.1 Information needs

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Project Partners

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Centre d'études et d'expertise sur les risques, l'environnement, la mobilité et l'aménagement Cerema	FRANCE
Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies LBTU	LATVIA
University of Latvia LU	LATVIA
Research Institutes of Sweden RISE	SWEDEN
University of Westminster UoW	UNITED KINGDOM
Malmö University MAU	SWEDEN
Grazer Energieagentur GmbH, Graz Energy Agency GEA	AUSTRIA
VTI/Sweden's national centre for research and education on public transport K2	SWEDEN
Power Circle PC	SWEDEN
University of Innsbruck UIBK	AUSTRIA

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1. Introduction

Information needs for the synthesis analysis in work package two (WP2) were mainly communicated to other work packages verbally at the internal project meetings and via feedback on others working material, such as interview protocols. An initial list of questions, was however, compiled (31.01.2023) and presented alongside the initial analytical framework for the project consortium in Bucharest (16.05.2023). Below, the final lists of data sources and questions are presented alongside instructions on how to use the questions when posing them to the material. The questions and other analysis material were distributed to project partners via a project internal document (22.12.2023).

2. Data sources

- WP1 Project overviews
- WP1 Questionnaire to ENUAC project leaders and interviews with ENUAC project partners
- WP2 ENUAC Call, ENUAC project proposals, and ENUAC second-year project reports
- WP3 Reports from roundtable discussions (national workshops)
- WP4 Word frequency analysis of ENUAC proposals and reports

3. Questions

1. What is the project about and what are its main **objectives & visions**?

Instructions: Here we want to get an understanding of what the project is about, what result- and impact objectives it has, and (if possible) the future visions the project idea is based on (such as car-free city center or equitable accessibility).

2. How are the notions of accessibility and connectivity **conceptualized**?

Instructions: What we primarily want to understand is whether the projects take a stance in relation to the concepts and, if so, what that stance is (e.g., *place-based* vs. *people-based accessibility*), and (if possible) how that stance influences the project's design (such as what the project chooses to focus on and measure).

3. Which accessibility and connectivity **problems** are covered, and how are these produced?

Instructions: What we want to understand is which accessibility and connectivity challenges the project chooses to focus on, how those challenges are described, and how the project justifies addressing/prioritizing them.

4. How are **coalitions/consortiums** built, and who is involved in what activities in which roles?

Instructions: We want to understand who has been involved in shaping the project proposal, who was planned to participate in which roles during implementation (including who has the mandate to do what), how it turned out, and who is intended to lead the transformation of project insights into activities contributing to transition (see question 5).

5. How are **experiments** set up, and what are their objectives?

Instruction: We focus on experiments in a broad sense (but are particularly interested in the term *living lab*). What we want to understand is how the project activities involving 'real-world actions' (e.g., dialogue with residents or testing new traffic regulations) were planned and intended to lead to, and how they turned out.

6. How are outputs from the project **transformed into action**, and by whom?

Instructions: We seek to understand how the project planned for the handling of knowledge, tools, and other developments during the project to contribute to transitions, and how it turned out. For example, how are recommendations developed and how are these intended to contribute to new types of decisions and activities after the project?

7. How does the project describe **urban context**, and how does this influence the project plan?

Instructions: We want to understand how the project describes urban contexts and the (unique) conditions for accessibility and connectivity they create, and how this affects the project plan including to whom and where insights should be disseminated. For example, are the project's insights described as relevant for municipalities across Europe or for some other group?